

Vibrational Spectra of Some Aminomethylpyridine Molecules

V. N. VERMA

Department of Physics, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.

Manuscript received 7 September 1977, revised 21 December 1977, accepted 22 February 1978

Infrared absorption spectra of 2-amino-3-methyl- and 2-amino-4-methylpyridines have been recorded in the liquid and KBr pellet respectively in the region $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The observed bands have been assigned to different modes of vibrations assuming C_s symmetry to these molecules. The change in the vibrational spectra due to substitution of amino- and methyl-groups simultaneously in the different positions in pyridine is discussed. The modes arising due to mutual interactions of the amino- and methyl-groups are presented in more explicit manner.

THE vibrational spectra of pyridine, aminopyridines and methylpyridines have been reported by many workers in literature¹⁻⁴. In general they have taken the similar atoms or group of atoms for the substitutions in pyridine and have discussed the effects of these substitutions on the vibrational spectra. It has been proposed here for the first time to study the change in the vibrational spectra due to substitutions of different groups of atoms i. e. amino- and methyl groups simultaneously in the different positions of pyridine molecule.

Experimental

The samples of 2-amino-3-methyl (liquid) and 2-amino-4-methyl-pyridine (solid) were obtained from Reilly Tar & Chemicals Corporation, U.S.A. and were used without further purification. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Grating Infrared Spectrophotometer Model 621 in the frequency range $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in liquid phase for 2-amino-3-methyl- and in KBr pellet for 2-amino-4-methylpyridine molecules. The infrared spectra are reproduced in Figs. 1 & 2.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Results and Discussion

The molecules belong to C_s point group under the mass point assumption of NH_2 and CH_3 groups. The 27 modes of fundamental vibrations can be divided into 19 a' (planar) and 8 a'' (non-planar) vibrations. There will arise a few more vibrations due to the internal vibrations in the amino- and methyl groups. The fundamental vibrations have been assigned to the different modes of vibrations on the basis of the intensity of the observed bands and the observed magnitudes of the various frequencies. The assignments of the fundamental frequencies of pyridine and its derivatives served as a guide line for the assignments in the present investigation. The amino group frequencies can be easily ascertained by the help of the assignments of the fundamental frequencies of aminopyridines² and of methyl group by the methylpyridines^{3,4}. The observed bands with their proposed assignments are presented in Table 1 & 2.

Out of the five C-H stretching vibrations of pyridine, normal coordinate calculation of Long et al.⁵ on monopyridine shows that the fundamental frequency 3036 cm^{-1} (a_1 species) is affected by the substitution and this becomes a C-X stretching mode. Only three C-H stretching frequencies are expected to be observed in the substituted pyridines and in general the bands are very weak. The bands observed at 3030 and 2990 cm^{-1} in 2-Amino-3-Methylpyridine (2A-3MP) are assigned to this C-H stretching mode of vibrations. But there is only one vibration observed at a magnitude of 3070 cm^{-1} in 2-Amino-4-Methylpyridine (2A-4MP) to this mode of vibration.

The C-N stretching vibration is reported at 1279 cm^{-1} in aniline⁶ and at $1320, 1335$ & 1310 cm^{-1} in 2-, 3- & 4-aminopyridines respectively. The magnitude of this mode of vibration is at 1198 cm^{-1} and at 1235 cm^{-1} in 2A-3MP and 2A-4MP respectively. Thus there is a decrease in the magnitude of this mode of vibration in the present molecules. It is expected due

TABLE 1—VIBRATIONAL ASSIGNMENTS FOR 2-AMINO-3 METHYL PYRIDINE MOLECULE.

Wave numbers (cm ⁻¹)	Intensity	Species	Assignments
497	75	a''	C-C-C o. p. bending
600	70	a''	C-C-C o. p. bending
700	50	a''	C-H o. p. bending
742	62	a''	N-H wagging
775	90	a''	CH ₃ twisting
872	30	a''	C-H o. p. bending
953	25	a''	C-H o. p. bending
996	55	a'	C-C ring breathing
1025	sh	a'	C-C-C i. p. bending
1034	45	a'	C-H i. p. bending
1080	60	a'	CH ₃ rocking
1137	40	a'	C-H i. p. bending
1198	65	a'	C-N stretching
1385	65	a'	CH ₃ symmetrical deformation
1450	100	a'	CH ₃ asymmetrical deformation
1478	90	a'	C-C stretching
1597	sh	a'	C-C stretching
1620	100	a'	N-H i. p. bending
2870	40	a'	CH ₃ symmetrical stretching
2925	sh	a'	CH ₃ symmetrical stretching
2950	50	a'	CH ₃ asymmetrical stretching
2980	50	a'	CH ₃ asymmetrical stretching
3030	70	a'	C-H stretching
3090	sh	a'	C-H stretching
3210	85		N-H i. p. bending + C-C stretching
3350	90	a'	N-H symmetric stretching
3485	75	a'	N-H asymmetric stretching

TABLE 2—VIBRATIONAL ASSIGNMENTS FOR 2-AMINO-4-METHYL-PYRIDINE MOLECULE.

Wave numbers (cm ⁻¹)	Intensity	Species	Assignments
445	100	a''	C-C-C o. p. bending
615	16	a''	C-C-C o. p. bending
700	52	a''	C-H o. p. bending
750	44	a''	N-H wagging
785	96	a''	CH ₃ twisting
856	70	a'	C-C ring breathing
960	48	a''	C-H o. p. bending
982	62	a'	C-C-C i. p. bending
1045	35	a'	C-H i. p. bending
1072	25	a'	CH ₃ rocking
1178	78	a'	C-H i. p. bending
1235	48	a'	C-N stretching
1370	68	a'	CH ₃ symmetric deformation
1440	100	a'	CH ₃ asymmetric deformation
1465	100	a'	CH ₃ asymmetric deformation
1488	60	a'	C-C stretching
1615	100	a'	C-C stretching
1640	100	a'	N-H i. p. bending
2920	62	a'	CH ₃ symmetric stretching
2980	60	a'	CH ₃ asymmetric stretching
3070	83	a'	C-H stretching
3150	95		N-H i. p. bending + C-C stretching
3315	85	a'	N-H symmetric stretching
3450	100	a'	N-H asymmetric stretching

to the mutual interaction of the amino- and methyl groups vibrations in the same region of spectrum.

The C-C stretching frequencies in pyridine and related compounds have been located in the region 1300-1600 cm⁻¹. An appreciable mixing of the C-C and C-N stretching modes take place as their magnitudes are nearly same. The strong bands were observed at 1470 cm⁻¹ in 2A-3MP and at 1488 cm⁻¹ in 2A-4MP.

These are corresponding to the C-C stretching vibration. The other C-C stretching vibration is at a magnitude of 1597 cm⁻¹ which is just like a shoulder in the case of 2A-3MP, but the same mode of vibration in 2A-4MP is of very high intensity at the magnitude of 1615 cm⁻¹.

The ring breathing vibration appears with medium strong intensity in the infrared spectra of almost all the substituted benzenes and pyridines. In pyridine it has

the same magnitude of 992 cm^{-1} as in benzene. The normal coordinate analysis by Long *et al.*⁵ shows this mode to be sensitive to the mass of the substituents. Experimental results on monosubstituted pyridines⁷ do not agree with the theoretical calculations of Long *et al.* It is clear from the experimental data that the magnitude of the ring breathing mode stays near to 990 cm^{-1} in mono-substituted pyridines wherein its magnitude is slightly higher. On the basis of these discussions the observed bands are reported here at 996 cm^{-1} for 2A-3MP and at 856 cm^{-1} for 2A-4MP respectively. An account has been taken into consideration of the assignments made by Green *et al.* for mono substituted pyridines⁴. The magnitude of this mode of vibration in 2-, 3- and 4- amino pyridines is reported at 980, 1005 and 985 cm^{-1} respectively and at 994, 1025 and 994 cm^{-1} in 2-, 3- and 4-methylpyridines respectively.

The frequencies arising due to C-H in-plane bending mode of vibrations are expected to be observed in the frequency range $1000\text{--}1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and those from the out-of-plane bending modes in the range $700\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The in-plane modes are observed with medium intensity at 1034 and 1137 cm^{-1} in 2A-3MP and at 1045 and 1178 cm^{-1} in 2A-4MP and the out-of-plane bending modes at 872 , 953 cm^{-1} for 2A-3MP and at 960 cm^{-1} for 2A-4MP. The magnitudes of these modes are nearly the same in the aminopyridines.

It is well established that the bands from the stretching vibrations of nitrogen atom against the hydrogen atoms of the amino group occur in the region $3200\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The magnitude of the N-H stretching frequencies may however be affected by the presence of weak hydrogen bonds. It has also been established by Zhukova and Shmahka⁷ that if perturbation is present in only one N-H bond there is a large change in the magnitude of the symmetrical frequency compared to the asymmetrical frequency. Symmetrical perturbation of both the N-H bonds leads to an identical decrease in symmetrical and asymmetrical stretching frequencies. On the basis of this conclusion they have shown that molecules of aromatic amines in the pure liquid state or in solution with proton acceptor solvents form complexes through intermolecular hydrogen bonds with the participation of one or both the hydrogens of the NH_2 group. This results in a shift of the N-H stretching frequencies to a lower region. Further the intramolecular hydrogen bonding has a little effect on the N-H stretching frequencies although it is partially responsible for an increase in the N-H bond angle⁸. If we see the nature of the observed bands in the present case, the theory is approved directly. The N-H symmetrical stretching vibration in the liquid and the solid are at 3350 and 3315 cm^{-1} and the asymmetrical stretching vibrations are at 3485 and 3450 cm^{-1} in 2A-3MP and 2A-4MP respectively. The N-H in-plane bending vibration is observed at 1620 and 1640 cm^{-1} in these two cases. In most of the amino compounds there is a strong band in the vicinity of 3200 cm^{-1} . This is due to the combination of the N-H in-plane bending mode and the C-C stretching mode. In the present investigation there is an experimental evidence that in 2A-3MP the N-H in-plane bending mode is combining with the

C-C stretching mode arising from the a_1 (1590 cm^{-1}) mode of pyridine. But in 2A-4MP the N-H in-plane bending mode is combining with the C-C stretching mode arising from the a_1 (1485 cm^{-1}) mode of pyridine. The magnitude of this mode is at 3210 cm^{-1} and 3150 cm^{-1} in 2A-3MP and 2A-4MP respectively. This is the combination vibration resonating with N-H symmetrical stretching vibration. Such a resonating frequency has been reported in many substituted anilines. Evans has observed this mode at 3230 cm^{-1} in aniline molecule.

The internal methyl group vibrations can be easily assigned. The symmetrical and asymmetrical stretching vibrations are observed at 2925 and 2950 cm^{-1} in 2A-3MP and at 2920 and 2980 cm^{-1} in 2A-4MP and at 2920 and 2980 cm^{-1} in 2A-4MP. The magnitude of this mode of vibration is at 2923 (Raman) and 2980 cm^{-1} in infrared spectra of 3-methylpyridine, at 2925 cm^{-1} (Raman) and 2950 cm^{-1} (Infrared) of 2-methylpyridine and at 2934 cm^{-1} (Raman) and 2970 cm^{-1} (Infrared) of 4-methylpyridine. The CH_3 deformation modes are observed at 1385 and 1450 cm^{-1} for 2A-3MP and at 1370 and 1440 cm^{-1} for 2A-4MP. The corresponding modes in 4-methylpyridine are at 1383 , 1445 and 1385 and 1452 cm^{-1} for 3-methylpyridine. The rocking mode is reported at 1080 cm^{-1} and at 1072 cm^{-1} in these two cases respectively. There is a possibility of twisting mode in the methyl group as reported and discussed by Colthup *et al.*⁹ in which no change in the internal angle occurs but the methyl group rotates back and forth around the bond which serves to join it to the rest of the molecule. The magnitude of this mode is observed at 775 and 785 cm^{-1} in 2A-3MP and 2A-4MP respectively. The values of this mode is reported at 744 , 804 cm^{-1} in 1,2,4-trimethylbenzene and at 753 and 810 cm^{-1} in 1,2,3-trimethylbenzene¹⁰.

The other bands observed in the present investigation is assigned to different modes of vibrations and shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, B. H. U. to provide the necessary facilities to record the spectra.

References

1. J. K. WILMSHURT and H. J. BERNSTEIN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1957, 35, 1183.
2. R. AMMNI AMMA, Ph D. Thesis, B H.U., 1970, "Spectroscopic Studies of Organic Molecules".
3. D. A. LONG, F. S. MURPIN, J. L. HALES and W. KYNASTON *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 53, 1171.
4. J. H. S. GREEN, W. KYNASTON and H. M. PAISLEY, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1963, 19, 549
5. D. A. LONG and W. O. GEORGE, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1963, 19, 1777.
6. J. C. EVANS, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1960, 16, 428.
7. E. L. ZHUKOVA and I. I. SHMAHKA, *Optics and Spectry.*, 1968, 25, 279.
8. S. F. MASON, *J. Chem. Soc. II*, 1958, 3619.
9. N. B. COLTHUP, L. W. DALY and S. E. WIBERLEY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", 2nd Edition 1975, Academic Press, page 221.
10. V. N. VERMA, *Spectry. Letts.*, 1975, 8, 349.